

THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC LEADERS IN ADOPTING THE STRATEGIC RENEWAL APPROACH TO IMPROVE IRAQI EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS / AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF THE OPINIONS OF A SAMPLE OF STRATEGIC LEADERS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF TIKRIT

OMAR WASFY¹, KIFAH ABBAS MIHEMEED², DR. AMMAR AWAD MOHAMMED³
and MOHAMMED SALIH HASAN⁴

¹Assistant Lecturer, College of Administration and Economics, University of Tikrit.
Email: cvvv32259@gmail.com.

²Assistant Professor, College of Administration and Economics, University of Tikrit.
Email: kefahljanabi@tu.edu.iq

³Assistant Professor, College of Administration and Economics, University, of Tikrit.
Email: am19ar83@yahoo.com

⁴Ph.D. Candidate Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Management of Sfax (FSEGS).
University of Sfax, Tunisi. Email: npx31mm0d@gmail.com

Abstract

The current study aims to examine the role played by strategic leaders in adopting the patterns of strategic renewal and all that is characterized by modernity to upgrade Iraqi educational organizations, diagnose defects and shortcomings and provide solutions. What is acceptable today is not to be acceptable tomorrow, as the most important feature that characterizes the world today is change. A successful organization is the one that has the ability to present and keep pace with everything that is new. Whenever the organization succeeds in that and accelerates the wheel of renewal it is to be capable to lead the competition it is in. Therefore, this study comes to identify the role of strategic leadership in supporting the speed of this wheel using the descriptive analytical method and adopts the deductive and inductive approach to reach the conclusions. The study comes out with a number of the most important conclusions which are that strategic leaders have a positive role in increasing the processes of strategic renewal in the research organization at the overall level, but it is not at the level required to support the radical renewal processes. The study also presents a set of proposals in light of these conclusions, the most important of which is the need to give the radical renewal processes a top priority by the strategic leaders in the organization under study, as it is one of the core duties of those leaders.

Keywords: strategic leaders, strategic renewal, radical renewal, Gradual renewal.

INTRODUCTION

If the organizations and developed countries in the field of finance and business are calling daily and across all forums for the necessity of change and presenting everything new despite their race in the field, then what should the organizations and developing and underdeveloped countries call for? There is no doubt that renewal has existed before the existence of business organizations and that it would not have existed without it. This fact is constant and does not need much research and we are not in the process of proving that, but what is required is how

organizations can carry out renewal processes at all levels, whether that renewal is radical (comprehensive) or gradual (partial), and who is primarily responsible for doing this?

There is no doubt that strategic renewal processes require the concerted efforts of all the employees in those organizations, especially the strategic leaders, who bear the bulk of the responsibility to direct the organization towards that. Thus, this study comes to identify the role played by the strategic leaders in supporting the strategic renewal processes in the researched organization through understanding the concepts of the subject and study its reality. In order to achieve the foregoing, the study includes four sections. The first section includes the study methodology represented by the problem, significance, aims and hypotheses emanating from it, as well as the sources of data collection, methods of collecting, the scientific method used to reach the conclusions, the definition of the field in question and justifications for its selection. As for the second section, it is devoted to defining the nature of strategic leadership and its most important functions. The third section includes the definition of the concept of strategic renewal and its patterns. The fourth section presents the most important conclusions and suggestions that the study has reached.

SECTION ONE

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The section includes the following items:

First: The study problem and its questions:

In an era in which the search for everything new is no longer the basic, constant, and decisive feature of organizations' survival and growth. What is considered acceptable yesterday in the field of business is no longer acceptable today, and what is considered acceptable today will not be accepted tomorrow? This fact has become one of the axioms of the twenty-first century. It is imperative for business organizations to continuously renew their work streams and conduct research and studies that support this. From here came the problem of the current study in the context of advancing the reality of Iraqi business organizations in general and educational ones in particular in the areas of strategic renewal by identifying the role that strategic leaders can play as the guiding head of the organization in supporting the strategic renewal processes, and to clarify the problem formulated within the following questions:

1. What is strategic leadership and strategic renewal?
2. What is the reality of strategic leadership and strategic renewal in Iraqi educational organizations?
3. What is the relationship between strategic leadership and strategic renewal in Iraqi educational organizations?
4. What is the impact of the relationship between strategic leadership and strategic renewal in Iraqi educational organizations?

Second: Significance of the study:

The importance of the study stems from the importance of the problem that it addresses. The more the problem is of great importance and is related to the existence and survival of the organization, the more important the study that examines the treatment of that problem. This introduction explains the importance of the current study because it is an attempt to accelerate the wheel of strategic renewal in the organization in question by identifying the role of strategic leadership in pushing that wheel and diagnosing the shortcomings in that role and presenting a set of conclusions and proposals in this regard. It can be said that the significance of this study emerges from two aspects:

A. Academic significance:

This is conducted by identifying the theoretical and conceptual frameworks for the subjects of the study, especially the concepts and patterns of strategic renewal, according to the point of view of the writers and researchers specialized in this field.

B. Field significance:

The process of conducting strategic renewal in universities through its three pillars (professor, student, and curriculum) and the research that is written in this regard can be considered the main wheel that drives this in all other sectors. This is due to the fact that the university can be considered the strategic leader of all organizations that achieves development and renewal in it. Therefore, diagnosing the imbalance and providing solutions and results affects all other sectors.

Third: Aims of the Study:

The current study aims to examine the role played by strategic leaders in adopting patterns of strategic renewal and all that is characterized by modernity to improve Iraqi educational organizations, diagnose defects and shortcomings, and provide solutions to them, as well as achieving the following:

1. Recognizing the nature of strategic leadership and strategic renewal, and understanding the philosophical aspects of them.
2. Diagnosing the reality of the study variables in the organization under study.
3. Identifying the nature of the relationship between strategic leaders and patterns of strategic renewal in the organization for the researcher.
4. Presenting a set of conclusions and suggestions that the study reaches for the researched organization in particular and the Iraqi academic organizations in general.

Fourth: The Hypotheses of the study:

The current study is based on two main hypotheses:

A. There is a direct correlation between strategic leadership and strategic renewal in the organization under study.

B. There is a significant influence relationship of the strategic leadership in the strategic renewal and its patterns in the organization in question.

Fifth: The Hypothetical Study Plan:

This item is exposed to the hypothetical study scheme, as shown in the figure below:

Figure (1): Hypothetical Study Scheme

Source: Prepared by Researchers

It is clear from Figure (1) that the study scheme consists of two main variables: strategic leadership as a main independent variable and strategic renewal as a main dependent variable as well as its patterns, which are considered as two sub-dependent variables. The figure also shows that there is a correlation and impact relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Sixth: Methodology and Method of Study:

The study adopts the deductive method in reaching conclusions, using the descriptive analytical method in presenting and analyzing data and information using the SPSS statistical package.

Seventh: Data collection methods:

The study has sought to search for all that is new from references represented by books, articles and researches issued by discreet magazines in the field of business administration, as well as official websites in the theoretical aspect. Then unpacked, analyzed and reached the results that were presented in the practical study. As for the practical side, the main tool for collecting data and information is the questionnaire that is designed in advance and then unloaded and analyzed to reach the results that are presented in the practical study.

Eighth: Scope of the Study:

It is represented by:

1. **Temporal limits:** The temporal limits of the study extended through the second half of the year 2021.
2. **Spatial limits:** the field study is confined to the University of Tikrit as the place covered by the study.

Ninth: Description of the investigated field and justifications for choosing:

The selection of the study population and sample is one of the basic issues facing researchers. For the environment to be suitable for studying the problem and testing the hypotheses, it requires the correct and rational identification of the sample approved for the study. This is one of the critical issues that may lead to the success or failure of the study. Tikrit university is chosen as an applied field of study since it is regarded as one of the vital pillars on which the society is based. It is a scientific academic organization distinct from the rest of the organizations as it is the tributary of most of these organizations and the rest of the community circles with qualified academic and practical staff who take their role in making these organizations achieve its goals and objectives in the light of which it is found to meet the needs and desires of the community.

A. A Brief about the researched field (Tikrit University):

Tikrit University was established on 23/11/1981. Since its establishment, the university has had an important role in implementing the policy of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in the field of education, scientific research and community service. The university's mission is to prepare generations of people with different specializations holding bachelors, masters and doctoral degrees, with specifications that accommodate the developments and transformations witnessed by the labor market in society. As for the university's objectives, they are consistent with the general objectives of higher education in terms of interest in scientific and educational research and community services through many bridges, while retaining other objectives that earn it a reputation and personality distinguishing it from other universities. In general, the objectives of the University are focused on the following:

1. Preparing qualified human resources with knowledge in the field of specialization, providing them with skills and knowledge relevant to the needs of society and making them capable of implementing the requirements of national development.
2. Updating the scientific curricula and educational methods that keep pace with the high movement of change in the environment and society.
3. Providing consultations and studies to ministries and state organizations and deepening scientific interaction with society and its scientific, industrial and service organizations.
4. Taking care of scientific research, nurturing and embracing talented and creative people and encouraging them.
5. Directing postgraduate programs towards the needs of society, its development prospects, and addressing its problems.
6. Documenting scientific and cultural relations locally, regionally and globally.

By reviewing the university's progress, we find that it has made strides towards achieving its academic and scientific goals.

B. Justifications for selection: The most important justifications for choosing Tikrit University as a field of study are as follows:

1. The consistency of the nature of the study and its objectives with the reality of universities and their academic leaders, both with regard to scientific and administrative activity. These are organizations characterized by a high degree of intellectual knowledge and experience that can be employed in the field of thinking, conclusion, and providing solutions, innovations and creativity.
2. Being one of the largest organizations in the governorate, having its organizational age, experiences and skills that qualify it as a better field of study. Moreover, it has a vital role in the community which has not stopped despite all the circumstances that our dear Iraq has gone through, which means the university's ability to keep pace with the changes that occur in the local and international environment.
3. Its endeavor, like other Iraqi universities, to adopt change as a strategy to accommodate the developments and transformations witnessed by the Iraqi environment in general and education in particular, to develop an appropriate vision for reforming the educational system and keeping pace with the accelerating scientific and cognitive development.
4. The university possesses a group of academic leaders who have the ability to present and disseminate creative ideas, innovations, research and knowledge, and this is consistent with the dimension of leadership characteristics formulas contained in the content of the research and testing the possibility of their application in the field reality.

SECTION TWO

STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP

First: Concept of Strategic Leadership

Strategic leadership is described as leadership that has the ability to predict, visualize, maintain flexibility, empower employees, and the ability to develop capabilities and competencies, improve organizational structures, select and develop the next generation of leaders, and sustain an effective organizational culture and ethical commitments (Ussahawanichakit, 2012:4). The essence of strategic leadership involves the ability to learn, the ability to change, with managerial wisdom, as it focuses on the people who bear the overall responsibility in the organization (Samim et al., 2019: 3). The concept of strategic leadership refers to those studied steps that directly aim to reach and achieve the company's vision or achieving at least part of it. This is performed by working to manage employees in a well manner and motivating and encouraging them to achieve this vision. The responsibility of this leadership is to build and shape the company's internal organizational structure (Retrieved, 2018:7).

The term strategic leadership is widely used to refer to a style of leadership or leadership at the higher management levels of the organization (Samim et al., 2019, 3). It is related to the leader's ability to anticipate, visualize, maintain flexibility and empower others to bring about comprehensive strategic change whenever the need arises (Mubarak & Yusoff, 2019:33).

Strategic leadership relates to the role and influence of individuals at higher organizational levels. It forms a bridge between the past, present and future, by re-emphasizing core values and identity to ensure continuity and integrity in work. Therefore, it has the ability to explain environmental disturbances and ambiguities, giving a meaningful image and providing a vision and road map that make the organization capable of developing and innovating. This is why some describe it as a dynamic and collective phenomenon whose impact extends beyond the pivotal organizational boundaries of the organization (Samim et. al., 2019: 3)

Second: Significance of Strategic Leadership

The importance of academic strategic leaders with their leadership skills is just as important as having the skill in education. It is of paramount importance that these leaders have the ability to manage educational environments and to get the most value from the educational system. In addition, a strategic leader should have an inspiring personality and the ability to excel and innovate, transparency, honesty, comprehensiveness and integrity, the ability to work hard to achieve strategic development plans, develop the skills of others, the ability to clearly express the strategic vision, identify the main goals according to their priorities and the participation of others in that, continuity in follow-up and development, and the ability to interact and communicate with teaching members, students, and outer society (Macklin, 2014: 27).

The importance of strategic leadership in the organization is also highlighted by sharing the organization's vision with others so that they follow it on their own through providing information, knowledge and methods to achieve that vision, and coordinating and balancing the conflicting interests of all members and stakeholders (Zakayo, 2017: xiii).

Third: The functions of strategic leadership: Strategic leadership is responsible for formulating the organization's strategy and charting its future. It is also seen as the main driver for the effective implementation of the strategy (Jooste & Fourie, 2009:51). Samim et. al. (2019:4-7) have specified eight functions for strategic leadership with other researchers adding other functions that can be stated as follows:

1. Making strategic decisions.
2. Dealing with external stakeholders.
3. Performing human resource management activities.
4. Motivation and influence.
5. Information management.
6. Operations management and supervision.
7. Managing social and ethical issues.
8. Managing conflicting requests.
9. Defining the strategic vision and direction of the organization (Mubarak & Yusoff, 2019:33).
10. Allocating FAO Resource Portfolio Benefits (Mubarak & Yusoff,2019:33).

SECTION THREE

STRATEGIC RENEWAL

The section consists of the following items:-

First: Concept of Strategic Renewal:

Strategic renewal has become a prominent subject in various organizations and administrative research fields in recent years (Schmitt et. al., 2018:81). It has become an urgent necessity for survival in today's business environment and for all business organizations, regardless of their field of work. Recent studies indicate that in order for any company to be able to survive in a dynamic environment, it must possess the ability to make improvements that align with its internal and external requirements (Sievinen et. al., 2019:1).

The name 'strategic renewal' consists of two terms that must be discussed. The first is "renewal" which means revitalizing, redistributing or replacing the existing organizational features of the organization. Through renewal, organizations explore and learn completely new ways that they use in investing their core capabilities and competitive methods (Järvi & Khoreva, 2020:11).

As for the second term, "strategy", it refers to actions aimed at transforming the core capabilities to contribute to achieving competitive advantage (Järvi & Khoreva, 2020:11). It is described as deductive and inferential consistency in decision-making behavior (Halonen et. al. 2019: 654). Despite the similarity with the business model, but there is a difference between them, as the business model does not explain the actual mechanisms of value generation or how to segment the market, evaluate the offer of excellence or cost leadership, or identify the vital systems in the organization. Business models are more general as well as can be relatively easier to imitate (Halonen et. al., 2019:654).

It is clear to us from the previous discussion that the concept of strategic renewal describes the results, content and processes of change in the organization that affect the ability of the organization to succeed in the long run (Friesl et. al., 2018:3). It is defined as the process that enables organizations to change their approved path by transforming their objectives and strategic capabilities (Schmitt et. al., 2018:81). It is the process of reconsidering organizational capabilities to achieve a balance between exploring and exploiting opportunities (Colabi & Khajeheian, 2018: 315). Colabi & Khajeheian (2018:318) define it simply as the innovation process within the organization. In general, there are three basic elements agreed by all of a explain the essence of the concept of strategic renewal: (Järvi & Khoreva, 2020:11):

1. Strategic renewal in particular involves a shift in the organization's core capabilities related to competitive advantage.
2. Strategic renewal concerns the entire organization.
3. Its outcomes extend across all organizational levels, which is vital to breaking the trajectory and ensuring the organization's long-term survival.

From the above, a procedural definition of strategic renewal can be developed as the process of radical renewal and modernization planned for all areas and activities of the university, especially the three basic pillars (professor, student, and curriculum) in a way that achieves a competitive advantage for the university that is difficult or impossible to imitate.

Second: The importance of strategic renewal at the present time:

Day by day, organizations need more and more in an urgent manner to transform and adapt from time to time in order to survive (Järvi & Khoreva, 2020: 16). Thus, strategic renewal is a key consideration in understanding the long-term survival and prosperity of the organization (Schmitt et al, 2018:81) because of the changes and developments in the business environment today that affect various industries. Renewal or changes in the field of digital, for example, have brought about a great impact and changes in various industries, which make it necessary for organizations to adapt to the diminishing demands of their previous cash-generating products and have led it to make difficult decisions, such as reducing energy productivity, restructuring and layoffs (Järvi & Khoreva, 2020:11). The broad interest in strategic renewal by all researchers and organizations today indicates that it is a vibrant and thriving field of research, however, increasing breadth also means an increasing diversity of theoretical perspectives and experimental contexts, which generates a number of challenges that impede the progress of this field, represented by the following (Schmitt et. al., 2018:81-82).

1. Theoretical Challenges: The plurality of concepts has not only led to conflicting definitions and assumptions, but also blurred the conceptual limit of this field.
2. Challenges resulting from the multiplicity of theory, which generates disturbances from different assumptions and results and contradictory particles. For example, some studies consider strategic renewal a purposeful process with a clear beginning and end, while other researchers describe strategic renewal as a continuous search to modify the intentions and capabilities of the organization.
3. Theoretical perturbations lead scientists to an only partial use of previous findings, which hinders the construction of knowledge accumulation. For example, Volberda and Lewin (2003) conclude that regeneration studies have become difficult to compare, assemble and reproduce.

Third: Patterns of strategic renewal:

Strategic renewal is an organized process whose aim is to organize the work of business organizations for the purpose of making changes in their future in proportion to environmental changes. Therefore, researchers mention many patterns of strategic renewal. Kirilka et. al. (2012:18) mention two types of strategic renewal used to achieve entrepreneurial work. First, the most important of which is continuous renewal, which includes the formation of new products that meet ambitions, new markets. The second is organizational renewal, which includes focusing on internal innovations that save more money and speed up operations. Despite the difference in determining the patterns of strategic renewal, they are all due to two main patterns (Xiao et. al., 2018:3):

1. Increasing (gradual) strategic renewal:

Increasing strategic renewal allows the organization to exploit opportunities by relying on improving the core business, and competition with performance outputs within the complete products and distinguished services. Thus, organizations can reuse existing resources and gradually renew their products and services in order to achieve adaptation to the new market environment, and reduces its need to make transformations later which are more difficult. In this area of renewal, organizations adopt ways of working related to introducing small and continuous improvements to their products (Volberda, 2016:2). In service organizations such as postal service organizations, they tend to gradually use modern technology in delivering mail to customers, such as using the internet to deliver magazines and newspapers to their customers in the global postal services market (Schmitt et.al., 2015: 6) and this transition is in effect. Even in Iraqi universities, the University of Tikrit today receives most of its mail, whether from the ministry or other universities through the internet, and strategic renewal is an organized process that aims at organizing the work of business organizations for the purpose of making changes in their future in proportion to environmental changes. Kirilka et. al. (2012:18) classifies strategic renewal into types used in entrepreneurial businesses, the most important of which are: continuous renewal (the formation of new products that meet ambitions and new markets) and organizational renewal (focusing on internal innovations that save more money and speed up operations).

2. Intermittent (radical) transformational strategic renewal:

In contrast to the increasing strategic renewal, the organization is required to replace one or more of its basic features or strategies. It addresses not only operational processes but also business models, technical foundations, organizational structures and capabilities, as well as other resources. In this field of renewal (which is also called exploratory innovation), organizations either find new ways of working or make relatively radical modifications to existing ways of working (Volberda, 2016:2). This type of renewal is essential for the organization to adapt to the changes in the industry because these sudden changes in the shape of the industry impose radically different competitive requirements (Schmitt et. al.,2015:7) and strategic renewal (which is carried out through the implementation of a new strategy for work) keeps pace with modern vernacular developments and redefines the scope by investing in new markets in areas geographically remote from competitive issues (Kirilka et. al.,2012:18).

3. Reasons why organizations must carry out strategic renewal:

The process of strategic renewal extends even to social systems within and outside organizations, so we find that people develop new relationships and break off old relationships. Behavioral patterns and expectations are constantly evolving (den Hond et. al., 2019:362). Strategic renewal is always necessary, especially in open systems, as the open system allows the occurrence of dynamic interactions between forces and environmental variables (Sarif & Zainudin, 2019:1), especially in light of digital transformation. Digital transformation, which is described as a continuous process of using new digital technologies in daily organizational life is also a key factor in strategic renewal (Warner & Wäger, 2019:1). Strategic renewal

enables the organization to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage especially in today's challenging business environment, such as global outsourcing, healthcare management, bribery, corruption, political risks, poverty and other challenges faced by organizations, as well as competitors who have new ideas and techniques to penetrate the market, which makes achieving sustainable competitive advantage for organizations a remote possibility based on the role of opportunity and luck as a possible explanation in achieving it (Järvi & Khoreva,2020:11).

SECTION FOUR

PRACTICAL FRAMEWORK

Testing Study Hypotheses

The third section includes a presentation of the results of the study by testing its hypotheses as in the following:

First: Testing the first hypothesis: This hypothesis can be tested through the following:

A. Testing the correlation between the variables at the macro level:

The results of Table (1) indicate the existence of a positive (direct) significant correlation between strategic leadership and strategic renewal at the total level in the organization in question. This is indicated by the value of the correlation coefficient of (0.564) at a level of significance (2.222), which is a significant value less than the hypothetical level of significance of the study amounting to (2.25). This means as a preliminary indicator that the adoption of strategic leadership by Iraqi universities contributes to increasing the strategic renewal processes carried out by the university at the macro level.

Table (1): The results of analyzing the correlations between strategic leadership and strategic renewal in the organization under study

Independent variable/dependent variable	Strategic leadership	P-Value
Strategic renewal	0.564**	0.000

N = 36

Source: Prepared by researchers depending on the SPSS statistical program results

B. Testing the correlation between the variables at the micro level:

This can be tested by:

1. Testing the correlation between the dependent variables:

The results in Table (2) also show a strong positive (direct) significant correlation between gradual renewal and radical renewal in terms of the value of the correlation coefficient (Spearman) with (0.769) at a level of significance (2.222), which is a significant value less than the hypothetical level of significance of the study (2.25). This indicates initially that there is a correlation between both types and that one of them may lead to the other.

Table (2): The results of analyzing the correlations between the dimensions of strategic renewal in the organization under study

Independent variable/dependent variable	Radical Renewal	P-Value
Gradual renewal	0.769**	0.000

N = 36

Source: Prepared by researchers depending on the SPSS statistical program results.

2. Testing the correlation between the dependent and independent variables:

The results shown in Table (3) also show a strong positive (direct) significant correlation between strategic leadership and both gradual renewal and radical renewal, respectively, in terms of the value of the correlation coefficient (Spearman) of (0.539) and (0.521), respectively, at a significant level (2.222), which is a significant value less than the significant hypothetical level of the study (2.25). This is a preliminary indicator that indicates that strategic leadership greatly influences the strategic renewal processes in the researched university. The factors that affect the independent variable are the same as the dependent variable, not the independent variable.

Table (3): The results of analyzing the correlations between strategic leadership and the patterns of strategic renewal in the organization under study

Independent variable/dependent variable	Radical Renewal	P-Value
Gradual Renewal	0.539**	0.001
Radical Renewal	0.521**	0.001

N = 36

Source: Prepared by researchers depending on the SPSS statistical program results.

Second: Testing the second hypothesis: The results of Table (4) indicate that strategic leadership has a positive significance in the strategic renewal processes in the researched organization at the overall level, and this effect confirms the calculated value (F) of (15,832) which is greater than its tabular value in significance (P-Value) of (2.222) at two degrees of freedom (1, 34) and a level of significance less or equal to (0.05). The value of the beta coefficient (β_1) amounts to (0.451), which is a significant value in terms of the calculated (t) value of (3.979).), which is greater than its tabular value in terms of (P-Value) of (0.000) at two degrees of freedom (1,34) and at a level of significance less or equal to (0.05). This indicates that the adoption of strategic leadership by one unit leads to an increase in support for operations by (0.451) in the organization under study, Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) of the model has reached (2.319), meaning that the strategic leadership explains approximately (32%) of the changes taking place in the strategic renewal processes and that (68%) of the changes are due to random variables not included in the model.

Table (4): The results of analyzing the impact of strategic leadership on strategic renewal in the organization under study

P-Value	Calculated F	R2	Strategic leadership		Independent variable/dependent variable
			β_1	β_0	
0.000	15.832	0.318	0.451 *(3.979) [0.000]	2.277 *(5.089) [0.000]	Total indicator of strategic renewal

D.f = (1, 34) N= 35 () refers to calculated t value [] refers to P- Value $P \leq 0.05$

Source: Prepared by researchers depending on the SPSS statistical program results.

As for the partial level, the results of the analysis in Table (5) show the following:

❖ **Strategic leadership** has a positive and significant effect on the gradual renewal of the organization under study, and this effect confirms the calculated (F) value of (13.819), which is greater than its tabular value in terms of (P-Value) of (2.222) at the two degrees of freedom (1,34) and the level of significance less than or equal to (2.25). The value of the beta coefficient (β_1) amounts to (2.414), which is a significant value in terms of calculated (t) amounting to (3.131), which is greater than its tabular value in terms of (P-Value), which is (2.221) at degrees of (1,34) and a level of significance less or equal to (2.25). The explanatory power of this model (R2) has reached a coefficient of determination (2.282), meaning that the strategic leadership explains (28%) of the changes that occur in the gradual renewal ,and that (61%)) of the changes in the gradual renewal are due to random variables that are not included in the model.

❖ **Strategic leadership** has a positive and significant effect on the radical renewal of the organization under study. This effect confirms the calculated (F) value of (12.652), which is greater than its tabular value in terms of (P-Value) of (0.001) at the two degrees of freedom (1,34) and the level of significance less than or equal to (0.05). The value of the beta coefficient (β_1) amounts to (0.428), which is a significant value with a calculated (t) value of (3.557), which is greater than its tabular value in terms of (P-Value) which is (0.001) at the two degrees of (1,34) and a level of significance less or equal to (0.05). The explanatory ability of this model (R2) has reached a coefficient of determination (0.271), meaning that the strategic leadership explains (27%) of the changes that occur in the radical renewal and that (63%)) of the changes in the radical renewal are due to random variables that are not included in the model.

Table (5): The results of analyzing the impact of strategic leadership on the patterns of strategic renewal in the organization under study

P-Value	Calculated F	R2	Strategic leadership		Independent variable/dependent variable
			β_1	β_0	
0.000	13.918	0.290	0.474 ** (3.731) [0.001]	2.245 ** (4.473) [0.000]	Gradual renewal
0.001	12.652	0.271	0.428 ** (3.557) [0.001]	2.310 ** (4.866) [0.000]	Radical renewal

D.f = (1, 34) N= 35 () refers to calculated t value [] refers to P- Value $P \leq 0.05$

Source: Prepared by researchers depending on the SPSS statistical program results.

Thus, the second hypothesis of the study is verified.

SECTION FOUR

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

First: Conclusions

1. It can be inferred initially that there is strategic renewal in organizations that have strategic leaders and that this presence increases with the increase in the number and competencies of these leaders due to the existence of a direct correlation between them.
2. There is a correlation between both gradual renewal and radical renewal, and that one of them may open up areas and prospects for doing the other.
3. Strategic leadership can be considered a crucial element in supporting the strategic renewal processes at the macro and micro levels in the organization under study, as the results show that there is a clear effect between the variables investigated, and the more one increases, the more the other increases.
4. The results of the analysis show that the role of strategic leaders in the gradual renewal processes is greater than in the radical renewal processes. This in itself can be considered a defect in the organization under study. Its strategic leaders do not give priority and status to radical renewal processes as it deserves which should be at the heart of the work of these leaders. The main reason for this is perhaps the association of the university with the ministry, which is the body who does this, and those leaders are not the ones who take the pivotal role.
5. There are many factors that lead and are affected by the strategic renewal processes, not just the strategic leadership. This is what has been discovered through the low value of the interpretation coefficient.

Second: Suggestions

1. The need for strategic leaderships to pay attention to radical renewal processes and give it the highest priority, as it is the most capable of doing so and fall within their responsibilities.

2. Ensuring the recruitment and appointment of individuals who are branded with the capabilities of strategic leaders because of their role in the processes of promoting strategic renewal.
3. Holding courses, conferences and seminars that enhance the capabilities and skills of strategic leaders in the areas of strategic renewal processes and patterns.
4. Training the employees of the organization under study at all organizational administrative levels, urging them to participate and present new ideas, and setting rewards and medals that are compatible with what the worker presents of new idea.
5. Linking the career path to the new ideas presented by the worker to obtain a higher rank in the career ladder.
6. Conducting several studies that examine the relationship between strategic renewal and other factors that affect it positively and negatively. Negative factors can be removed and positive factors can be strengthened , such as studying the role of subordinates in strategic renewal processes.

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